

Cyclopia pubescens Eckl. & Zeyh. Honeybush

Decoding
South Africa's
Biodiversity

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Group: Eudicot

Size: Up to 2 meters (height).

Distribution:

Foot of Van Stadens River Mountains, west of Gqeberha (Port Elizabeth) .

Importance:

Cyclopia pubescens is endemic to South Africa and has historically been used by the Khoi-San for its medicinal properties. Recent research done by the ARC identified it as a valuable species to add as a commercial cultivated species for beverage products. This species only occurs in small pockets in the Nelson Bay Metropole (Gqeberha) and is critically endangered.

PromethION Sequencing Report:

Output: 80.79 Gigabases

Approximate N50: 15.79 kilobases

Draft Genome Assembly Statistics:

Assembler used: Hifiasm

Genome Length: 2.29 Gigabases

BUSCO completeness score: 99.5% [Single: 13.9%, Duplicated: 85.6%]

BUSCO database: viridiplantae

Assembly N50: 9 938.21 kilobases

Contig number: 656

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